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EVIDENCE-BASED E-PLANNING FOR CLIMATE-RESILIENT CITIES: REMOTE SENSING
AND SPATIAL CONTEXT ANALYSIS OF DIVERSE NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS
INTERVENTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Urban planners increasingly rely on digital tools to design climate-resilient and biodiversity-supportive interventions, however empirical evidence on how spatial context influences the performance of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) remains limited. Understanding these contextual dynamics is essential for developing e-planning strategies that respond effectively to climate and ecological pressures. This study applies a remote-sensing-based and multi-buffer spatial analysis framework to assess the environmental context surrounding diverse NBS interventions across European cities. Using Sentinel-2 imagery, three spectral indices Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI), and Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI) were calculated within 100 m, 300 m, and 500 m buffers so as to capture micro, meso, and macro-scale spatial dynamics. NDVI and NDMI are interpreted as indicators of vegetation vitality and moisture availability, while NDBI reflects built-up intensity and the degree of urban encroachment on vegetated areas. Results reveal clear spatial gradients across sites: higher NDVI and NDMI values are associated with cooler microclimatic conditions and stronger ecological continuity, whereas elevated NDBI values indicate landscape fragmentation and reduced biodiversity support potential. By linking spectral indices to interpretable environmental conditions, the study demonstrates how standardized spatial context analysis enhances decision-making in urban e-planning by offering a scalable approach which is adaptable to diverse urban contexts. These findings provide planners with actionable insights for prioritizing greening interventions, identifying ecologically vulnerable areas, and monitoring climate adaptation outcomes.